

**OPERATSIYADAN KEYINGI VENTRAL CHURRA DAVOLASHDA
JARROHLIK TAKTIKASINI TANLASHNING ZAMONAVIY
YONDASHUVLARI**

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Operatsiyadan keyingi ventral churralar (OKVC) qorin devori jarrohligida eng ko‘p uchraydigan asoratlardan biri hisoblanadi. Laparotomiyalardan so‘ng ularning rivojlanish chastotasi 10–20% ni tashkil etadi, xavf guruhidagi bemorlarda esa (semizlik, qandli diabet, birlamchi operatsiyaning infeksiyon asoratlari) 30–40% ga yetishi mumkin [1,2]. Ushbu patologiya nafaqat tibbiy, balki muhim ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy muammo bo‘lib, uzoq muddatli mehnat qobiliyatini yo‘qotishga, hayot sifatining pasayishiga va tiklovchi operatsiyalarga katta xarajat qilinishiga olib keladi [2].

Gerniyoplastikaning zamonaviy usullari — to‘r implantlar yordamida tarangsizliksiz plastika va laparoskopik texnologiyalar keng joriy etilganiga qaramay, jarrohlik davolashdan so‘ng takrorlanish chastotasi 10–30% darajasida qolmoqda [1,3,5]. Buning asosiy sabablaridan biri optimal jarrohlik taktikasini tanlashning yagona standartlashtirilgan algoritmi yo‘qligidir [5,7].

Gerniyoplastikaning asosiy usullari

Ochiq gerniyoplastika tarixan OKVC davolashning asosi bo‘lib kelgan. Onlay usulida to‘r implant aponevrozning ustiga, teri ostiga joylashtiriladi. Ushbu usul oddiyliги bilan ajralib tursa-da, seroma hosil bo‘lishi (30–40%) va takrorlanish xavfi yuqori bo‘lganligi sababli katta o‘lchamdagi churralarda qo‘llash tavsiya etilmaydi [4,8,18].

Sublay texnikasi — to‘r implantni retromuskulyar yoki peritoneal oldi bo‘shlig‘iga joylashtirish — hozirda ochiq plastikaning «oltin standarti» sifatida tan olingan [1,5,17,18]. Bu usul implantning to‘qimalarga yaxshi integratsiyasini, seroma va takrorlanish xavfining kamayishini ta‘minlaydi [8,17,18].

Laparoskopik IPOM (Intraperitoneal Onlay Mesh) usuli 1990-yillarning oxiridan keng qo'llanila boshlagan [3,19]. Uning afzalliklari — to'qimalarga minimal shikast yetkazish, qisqa kasalxona muddati, yarali asoratlarning kamayishi — ayniqsa o'rta o'lchamdagi churralarda ochiq aralashuvlarga munosib muqobil bo'lib kelmoqda [3,19].

eTEP (extended Totally Extraperitoneal) texnikasi esa laparoskopik kirish yo'li orqali to'r implantni retromuskulyar bo'shliqqa joylashtirishga imkon beradi va ochiq Sublay usulining biomexanik afzalliklarini minimal invaziv yondashuv bilan birlashtiradi [1,16,20].

To'r implant va fiksatsiya usulini tanlash

Zamonaviy gerniyoplastikada to'r implantni to'g'ri tanlash muolajaning samaradorligini ko'p jihatdan belgilaydi [5,7,13].

Polipropilen to'rlar mustahkamligi va biologik muvofiqligi bilan ajralib turadi, ammo qorin ichiga joylashtirilganda adeziogen xususiyatlar namoyon etadi [3,19].

Qisman so'riladigan va antimikrob qoplamali implantlar infeksiyon asoratlar va surunkali og'riq xavfini kamaytiradi [12,13,20].

Fiksatsiya usullari — transfiksatsion tikuvlar, apparatli fiksatsiya (takerlar) va yelim fiksatsiyasi — xavf-foyda nisbati bo'yicha differensial baholanishi kerak [3,12,19].

Xulosa

OKVC davolash — yagona universal yechimga ega bo'lmagan murakkab klinik vazifa [1,5,15].

Bemor xususiyatlari va churra nuqsonining morfologiyasini hisobga olgan holda jarrohlik taktikasini tanlashning shaxsiylashtirilgan, klinik jihatdan asoslangan algoritmini ishlab chiqish zamonaviy gerniologiyaning dolzarb muammosi bo'lib, ushbu dissertatsiya tadqiqotining asosiy maqsadini tashkil etadi [5,7,14].

Bunday algoritm operatsiya oldidan rejalashtirish jarayonini standartlashtirish, takrorlanish va asoratlar chastotasini kamaytirish imkonini beradi [14,15,20].

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